

Star-forming activity and interstellar medium conditions of the [OIII]-selected galaxies before the peak epoch

based on Suzuki et al. (2017) to be submitted

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Galaxy formation before the peak epoch

$z \sim 3 - 3.6$

How physical conditions (e.g. star-forming activity and ISM conditions) of galaxies evolve towards the peak epoch?

→ It has been investigated using UV-selected galaxies.

Madau & Dickinson 2014

Specific SFR

Tasca+2015

Gas metallicity

Onodera+2016

and also

Maiolino et al. (2008);
 Mannucci et al. (2009);
 Stark et al. (2013)
 Troncoso et al. (2014);
 Nakajima et al. (2016)
 and more...

[OIII] : useful tracer of star-forming galaxies

- High- z star-forming galaxies have stronger [OIII] λ 5007 emission (e.g. Steidel+14; Shimakawa+15; Shapley+15; Holden+16; Kashino+17; Strom+17...)
- Not significantly affected by dust extinction

Narrow-band [OIII] emitter imaging at $z > 3$

Mahalo-Subaru (Kodama+13; Tadaki+13)

- SXDF-UDS-CANDELS ►
- NB209, NB2315 (MOIRCS)
- $z = 3.18, 3.62$ [OIII] emitters
- HST/WFC3 H-band images

☆ HiZELS (Sobral+13; Khostovan+15)

- COSMOS field
- NBK (WFCAM)
- $z = 3.24$ [OIII] emitters
- Wide field survey (1.6 deg²) ►

and also Tepliz et al. (1999), Maschietto et al. (2008)

Star-forming activity of [OIII] emitters

Stellar mass — SFR relation of [OIII] emitters at $z \sim 3.24$ (●) and $z \sim 2.23$ (▲).

- Stellar mass : SED fitting

- SFR : from the rest-frame UV luminosity

- Dust extinction : UV slope β

- (Almost) constant normalization between the two epochs
- [OIII] emitters at $z = 3.24$ show an offset along the main sequence

NIR spectroscopy with Keck/MOSFIRE

- H and K-band spectroscopy
 - Integration time : 1.5 and 2 hours for H and K band
 - Ten [OIII] candidate emitters with one mask
 - All candidates are identified as [OIII] emitters at $z = 3.22 - 3.27$
- **High efficiency of follow-up observations of NB-selected sources**

ISM conditions of [OIII] emitters

Comparison with UV-selected galaxies and Ly α emitters at $z > 3$

- Similar ISM conditions as the UV-selected galaxies with similar stellar masses (Onodera+16)
- At $\log(M_*/M_{\text{sun}}) \sim 9.1 \rightarrow$ consistent with Ly α emitters (Nakajima+16)

Mass – Metallicity relation at $z > 3$

- $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H}) \rightarrow$ Calibration method by Curti et al. (2017)

Solid lines : Empirical relations between each line ratio and $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$

Mass – Metallicity relation at $z > 3$

- $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H}) \rightarrow$ Calibration method by Curti et al. (2017)
- Lower gas metallicity than local galaxies at a fixed stellar mass : ~ -0.6 dex
- Small scatter

Mass – Metallicity relation at $z > 3$

- $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H}) \rightarrow$ Calibration method by Curti et al. (2017)
- Lower gas metallicity than local galaxies at a fixed stellar mass : ~ -0.6 dex
- Small scatter
- Consistent with Onodera et al. (2016)

Comparison with $z \sim 2$ samples

LAEs and LBGs at $z=2-3$
from Nakajima & Ouchi (2014)

Cullen et al. (2014)
: 3D-HST H-band grism spectroscopy

- $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H}) \rightarrow$ Kobulnicky & Kewley (2004) method
: Two solutions of ($\log(q)$, $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$)
- Nakajima & Ouchi (2014), Cullen et al. (2014) \rightarrow using the same method
: **Similar ionization parameters and $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$**

Summary: Evolution from $z \sim 3.2$ to $z \sim 2$

- No strong evolution of star-forming activity and gas metallicities from $z \sim 3.2$ to $z \sim 2$ at a fixed stellar mass.

- There is an offset along the main sequence.

→ Their physical conditions change as their stellar masses increase along the same scaling relations between the two epochs.

= **Stellar masses might be a primarily quantity to describe the evolutionary stages of galaxies at higher redshifts ($z > 2$).**